

The HuT

Consortium meetings n.3

Deliverable D7.8

DEVELOPED WITHIN

WP7 Coordination and Management, T7.5 Consortium meetings

AUTHORS

Michele Calvello (UNISA); Alfonso Rossi Filangieri (UNISA)

Version 1.0

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1. Technical references

Project Acronym	The HuT
Project Title	The Human-Tech Nexus - Building a Safe Haven to cope with Climate Extremes
Project Coordinator	Michele Calvello UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI SALERNO mcalvello@unisa.it
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- * PU = Public
PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)
CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

1.1. Document history

Version	Date	Lead contributor	Description
0.1	02.12.2024	Michele Calvello (UNISA)	First draft
0.2	17.12.2024	Guido Rianna (CMCC)	Critical review and proofreading
1.0	18.12.2024	Michele Calvello (UNISA)	Final version

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none

3. Annual meeting in Gerzensee (Switzerland)

3.1. Location and participants

The HuT end-of-year-two consortium meeting has been held on November 20-22, 2024, at Gerzensee (Switzerland).

Table 1: Participant list

ID	Acronym	Name	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3
1	UNISA	Michele Calvello	yes	yes	yes
1	UNISA	Gaetano Pecoraro	yes	yes	yes
2	CMCC	Alessio Menini	yes	yes	yes
2	CMCC	Guido Rianna	yes	yes	yes
2.1	CNR	Valentina Bacciu	yes	yes	yes
3	HEREON	Jo-Ting Huang-Lachmann	yes	yes	yes
3	HEREON	Anke Schluensen-Rico	yes	yes	yes
3	HEREON	Cicilia Steffi Lukman	yes	yes	yes
4	GFZ	Laurens Oostwegel	yes	yes	yes
4	GFZ	Danijel Schorlemmer		yes	yes
5	IIASA	Joanne Linnerooth-Bayer	yes	yes	yes
5	IIASA	Florian Kraxner	yes	yes	yes
5	IIASA	Andrey Krasovskiy	yes	yes	yes
5	IIASA	Juliette Martin	yes	yes	yes
6	UPC	Marcel Hurlimann	yes	yes	yes
6	UPC	Alex Flavio Asurza	yes	yes	yes
7	UPV	Adria Rubio-Martin	yes	yes	yes
7	UPV	Manuel Pulido-Velazquez	yes	yes	yes
7	UPV	Ana Gabriela Fernandez Garca	yes	yes	yes

7	UPV	Eric Gielen	yes	yes	yes
8	NGI	Luca Piciullo	yes	yes	
9	GWP-CEE	Stanislav Hronček	yes	yes	yes
11	IMO	Harpa Grímsdóttir	yes	yes	yes
11	IMO	Helga Ívarsdóttir	yes	yes	yes
12	VU	Gintautas Stankunavicius	yes	yes	yes
12	VU	Giedre Godiene	yes	yes	yes
13	ARANTEC	Eisharc Jaquet	yes	yes	yes
13	ARANTEC	Francis Nieto Torres	yes	yes	yes
14	KOTIVIZIG	Janos Agocs	yes	yes	yes
14	KOTIVIZIG	David Bela Vizi	yes	yes	yes
14	KOTIVIZIG	Attila Lovas	yes	yes	yes
14	KOTIVIZIG	Péter Gergő Katona	yes	yes	yes
14	KOTIVIZIG	Péter Sólyom	yes	yes	yes
15	ICONS	Ilaria Bonetti	yes	yes	yes
15	ICONS	Erica Moresco	yes	yes	yes
16	LEITHA	Francesco Lo Conti	yes	yes	yes
18	CONF-NO	Francesca Cossu	yes	yes	yes
20	MA	Urdur Gunnarsdottir	yes	yes	yes
21	UNIGE	Jogscha Abderhalden	yes	yes	yes
21	UNIGE	Julia Josselyn Aguilera Rodriguez	yes	yes	yes
21	UNIGE	Elias Huland	yes	yes	yes
21	UNIGE	Mario Bruno Rohrer	yes	yes	yes
21	UNIGE	Anna Scolobig	yes	yes	yes
21	UNIGE	Markus Stoffel	yes	yes	yes
22	UCL	Carina Fearnley	yes	yes	yes
22	UCL	Ilan Kelman	yes	yes	yes
22	UCL	Maryam Rokhideh	yes	yes	yes
23	MET	Joanne Robbins	yes	yes	yes

24	BGS	Katy Freeborough	yes	yes	yes
25	GNDR	Shivangi Chavda	yes	yes	yes
*	LAP (and MET)	Brian Golding	yes	yes	yes
*	LAP	Manfred Staehli	yes		yes
*	LEAP	Jonathan Pratschke	yes	yes	yes
*		Christophe Lienert			yes
*		Veronika Schick		yes	
*		Marco Vanoni		yes	
*		Enrique Vidal Rosso	yes	yes	yes

Note: Other people from consortium partners attended online some parts of the meeting.

3.2. Agenda

Wednesday 20 November

- LUNCH
- 14:30-15:00, **Welcome and introduction to the meeting**
- 15:00-16:30, **Activities in the Demonstrators (part 1)**
- COFFEE BREAK
- 17:00-18:30, **Activities in the Demonstrators (part 2)**
- Free time and networking
- DINNER

Thursday 21 November

- 09:00-09:30, **WP3: Governance and Policy**
- 09:30-10:20, **International DRR Nexus Forum (part 1)**
- COFFEE BREAK
- 10:50-13:00, **International DRR Nexus Forum (part 2)**
- LUNCH
- 14:30-15:00, **WP2: Human behaviours**
- 15:00-15:30, **WP4: Science and technology**
- 15:30-16:00, **WP1: Demonstrators' arena**
- COFFEE BREAK
- 16:30-17:00, **WP6: Communication, dissemination and exploitation**
- 17:00-17:30, **WP5: Transferability and scalability**
- 17:30-18:30, **Discussion: "Towards a more integrated approach"**
- Free time and networking
- DINNER

Friday 22 November

- 09:00-09:30, **General Assembly (WP7)**
- 09:30-11:00, **Looking ahead: consortium duties for next reviewing term**
- COFFEE BREAK
- 11:30-12:00, **Invited presentation: Swiss disaster risk management system**
- 12:00-13:00, **Looking ahead: The HuT KERs**
- LUNCH

3.3. Activities

All the activities listed on the Agenda have been carried out. The presentations are shared internally using the google drive platform (see Deliverable 7.2 – Data management plan, <https://zenodo.org/records/10029991>)

3.3.1. Work Packages (WPs)

All the activities that are being conducted in the seven WPs were presented in the meeting.

Work package WP1 – Demonstrators’ arena. The following themes were presented and discussed in this session, on the second day of the meeting.

1. Fast-track implementation of DRR actions
2. Local DRR-nexus Forums (L-DRRnF): a roadmap of ten demonstrators
3. Local data portals
4. 'The HuT for Me and You'
5. End-to-end evaluation of existing warning systems

Work package WP2 – Human behaviours. The following themes were presented and discussed in this session, on the second day of the meeting.

1. News and overview of activities in 2024
2. Need for Systemic Thinking of Warning Systems
3. Next steps

Work package WP3 – Governance and policy. The following themes were presented and discussed in this session, on the second day of the meeting.

1. Enablers and barriers to multi-hazard/systemic risk reduction
2. Robust decision support tools for multi/systemic risk policy making
3. Insurance and risk financing instruments for DRR and local resilience

Work package WP4 – Science and Technology. The following themes were presented and discussed in this session, on the second day of the meeting.

1. Performed activities and lessons learnt
2. Documenting the DEM activities using the Logbook
3. Dynamic exposure mapping
4. Working groups on monitoring and modelling

Work package WP5 – Transferability and scalability. The following themes were presented and discussed in this session, on the second day of the meeting.

1. Second year overview
2. International DRR nexus Forum (I-DRRnF)
3. Field visits
4. Amplifying framework
5. Science-Art

6. Next steps

Work package WP6 – Communication, dissemination and exploitation. The following themes were presented and discussed in two sessions, on the second and third day of the meeting.

1. Overview and Status of activities
2. Monitoring: WEI, CEI, PEI, SEI
3. Consolidation of the Exploitation Strategy
4. Exploitation Workshop: The HuT KERs

Work package WP7 – Coordination and Management. Coordination and management issues were addressed throughout the meeting, whenever needed, yet the main sessions devoted to these issues were the following.

- Intro to The HuT annual meeting (first day)
- General Assembly (third day)
- Looking ahead: consortium duties for reviewing term ending in May 2025 (third day)

3.3.2. Demonstrators (DEMs)

A session in the first day of the meeting was specifically devoted to the following 10 Demonstrators

DEM 1 – Valencia (Spain). Investigated climate extremes: droughts, heatwaves.

DEM 2 – Val d’Aran Region (Spain). Investigated climate extremes: droughts, floods, forest fires, landslides.

DEM 3 – Lattari mountains (Italy). Investigated climate extremes: floods, forest fires, landslides, storms.

DEM 4 – Vilnius (Lithuania). Investigated climate extremes: floods.

DEM 5 – Schleswig-Holstein State (Germany).

DEM 6 – East fjords (Iceland). Investigated climate extremes: floods, landslides.

DEM 7 – Tisza River Basin (Hungary). Investigated climate extremes: floods.

DEM 8 – Ogliastra (Italy). Investigated climate extremes: droughts, forest fires, heatwaves.

DEM 9 – Dorset (UK). Investigated climate extremes: floods, landslides, storms.

DEM 10 – Berne Canton (Switzerland). Investigated climate extremes: floods, landslides, storms.

The DEM leaders presented the activities that are being carried out in their territories following a common template purposefully devised to outline how they contribute to the main tasks that are present in the first five WPs of the project. The template included slides for “ongoing activities” and “planned activities” in relation the following tasks:

- WP1: The Hut for Me and You, Local data portals
- WP2: Warning systems, Public engagement, Cultural changes
- WP3: Enablers and barriers, Decision support tools, Insurance
- WP4: Monitoring, Modelling
- WP5: Amplifying story, Field visits

3.3.3. International DRR Nexus Forum (I-DRRnF) workshop

The morning of the second day of the meeting was devoted to the second edition of the International DRR Nexus Forum workshop, entitled “Enhancing multi-hazard DRR efforts through nature-based solutions and multi-hazard early warning systems”. More details on the workshop are available in deliverable D.5.7 - “Minutes from the I-DRRnF workshops n.2”.

3.3.4. General Assembly

The third General Assembly of The HuT was held on Friday 22 November 2024, during the third day of the meeting. Table 2 shows the list of participants.

Table 2: Participants in General Assembly

Partner	Name
UNISA	Michele Calvello
CMCC	Guido Rianna
CNR	Valentina Bacciu
HEREON	Jo-Ting Huang-Lachmann
GFZ	Danijel Schorlemmer
IIASA	Joanne Linnerooth-Bayer
UPC	Marcel Hurlimann
UPV	Manuel Pulido-Velazquez
NGI	Luca Piciullo
GWP-CEE	Stanislav Hronček
HY	Janina Kayhko
IMO	Harpa Grímsdóttir
VU	Gintautas Stankunavicius
ARANTEC	Eisharc Jaquet
KOTIVIZIG	Peter Gergo
ICONS	Ilaria Bonetti
LEITHA	Francesco Lo Conti
SOR	(apologies)
CONF-NO	Francesca Cossu
NIP	(apologies)

MA	Urdur Gunnarsdottir
UNIGE	Anna Scolobig
UCL	Carina Fearnley
MET	Joanne Robbins
BGS	Katy Freeborough
GNDR	Shivangi Chavda

The General Assembly has given mandate to coordinator and project manager, already initiated, to finalize a request to amend the Grant Agreement. The latter was needed because one partner of the Consortium the “Norwegian Geotechnical Institute” (legal name: Stiftelsen Norges Geotekniske Institutt, PIC 998866522) changed its official name and PIC number, as follows:

- legal name Norges Geotekniske Institutt AS
- PIC 879085975

3.3.5. Main conclusions

Based on what was presented and discussed over the three days, the partnership did not identify any specific critical issue. The activity plan up to the next review, set for month 32 (May 31, 2025), has been agreed upon and defined. The deliverables and the activities to be carried out in the coming months are expected to proceed as planned.

A key topic of discussion was the method by which information is shared and transmitted between demonstrators and between demonstrators and WP/Task leaders. To facilitate the clear and systematic circulation of information, a partial reorganization of the currently operational tools (Logbook and DMB-CDE meetings) will be implemented. The Logbook will be restructured to enable easier consultation and feedback on interim progress by individual demonstrators. The DMB-CDE meetings will become the only regular consortium-wide online meetings we will schedule in the coming year. The meetings will last 2 hours and will be held every two months, on Mondays, starting at 14:30 CET. The calendar of the 2025 DMB-CDE meetings is the following

- Monday 20/01/2025, 14:30-16:30 CET
- Monday 24/03/2025, 14:30-16:30 CET
- Monday 19/05/2025, 14:30-16:30 CET
- Monday 21/07/2025, 14:30-16:30 CET
- Monday 20/10/2025, 14:30-16:30 CET
- Monday 15/12/2025, 14:30-16:30 CET

Both WP leaders and DEM leaders will participate and contribute to the DMB-CDE meetings, considering the following fixed AGENDA:

14:30 - 15:00. Brief presentations by the six WP leaders (5' each) on WP activities and other feedback, based on logbooks

15:00 - 15:10. BUFFER (to account for delays, questions, or technical problems)

15:10 - 16:10. Six agenda items (10' each) focusing on flagship activities worth highlighting for proper promotion or to address specific issues, e.g., amplification, exploitation, related to the following 6 topics:

- (Topic 1) "The HuT for me and you" narratives, Stakeholders and public engagement
- (Topic 2) Amplification, Field Visits
- (Topic 3) Web portals, Monitoring, Modelling
- (Topic 4) Warning systems, including end-to-end evaluation
- (Topic 5) NbS, Climate proofing, MCDA, Insurance
- (Topic 6) CDE

16:10 - 16:20. BUFFER (to account for delays, questions, or technical problems)

16:20 - 16:30. Other logistical matters or consortium-related topics of interest

Finally, a few clusters of activities have been identified to bring together working groups that are simultaneously engaged in developing approaches and tools focused on complementary topics. For instance, the development of serious gaming (further expanded to account for various hazards) can also be considered an integral part of the training activities that will be conducted in WP2. In the coming weeks, it will also be important to consolidate the plan for the remaining Field Visits considering the similarities among DEMs, ambitions, and developments.

